

Research Article

Sexual Risk Behaviours among Young People with Adverse Childhood Experiences in Ibadan, Nigeria.

Ige, Olusimbo Kehinde¹, Ilesanmi, Olayinka Stephen*¹ and Adebayo, Ayodeji Matthew²

¹Department of Community Medicine, University College Hospital, Ibadan, Nigeria

²Department of Community Health, Federal Medical Centre, Owo, Nigeria

*Corresponding Author's E-mail: ileolasteve@yahoo.co.uk, Phone Number: 08032121868

Abstract

This study aimed to examine the association between adverse childhood experiences (ACE) and sexual risk behaviours and sexual re-victimization among young people. A cross-sectional survey of 347 young people residing in a low socioeconomic urban community in Ibadan, Nigeria was conducted. Predictors of sexual risk behaviour and sexual re-victimization after the age of 16 years were determined with logistic regression analysis. At least one form of adverse experience was reported by all respondents. The order of occurrence was: physical neglect (98%), emotional abuse (38.3%), physical abuse (35.7%) and sexual abuse (29.1%) and emotional neglect (28.8%). In all, 15.0% reported at least one risky sexual behaviour. The risk factors for sexual risk behaviours were: age ≥ 20 years [OR: 9.8 (3.8- 25.6)], lack of family connectedness [OR: 4.2(1.5-11.6)] and history of child sexual abuse [OR: 6.9(3.5-14.1)]. The odds of sexual risk behaviour increased by 2.3(1.7-3.2) with each additional ACE reported. Child sexual abuse [OR 12.1(4.4-32.7)] was the only risk factor for sexual re-victimization. Our findings support the evidence of the interrelatedness of child sexual abuse, lack of parental connectedness and subsequent sexual risk behaviour particularly with increasing age. A cycle of sexual re-victimisation was also identified. These suggest preventive targets for victimised children.

Keywords: adverse childhood experiences; sexual behaviours; sexual re-victimization; young people; Nigeria

Introduction

Helping individuals cope with adverse childhood experiences (ACE) presents a serious public health challenge, due to the several potential life threatening physical and psychological effects of such experiences. Although some effects of child maltreatment are apparent in the short term, less visible negative outcomes often emerge during the course of victims' lives (Chalk, Gibbons, & Scarupa, May 2002). Many health and social problems including risky sexual behaviour have been shown to have childhood origins (Anda, et al., 2006; Edwards, et al., 2005; Sapp & Vandeven, 2005). Many of these compensatory behaviours have been put in place as solutions to traumatic life experiences during childhood (Forrester, 2010). These health risk behaviours also lead to more medical problems, with various public health implications.

Adverse childhood experiences (ACEs) are stressful and traumatic exposures affecting the development of children and these include growing up in dysfunctional households; abuse (emotional, physical, sexual), and neglect (emotional, physical) (Anda, et al., 2006; Edwards, et al., 2005; Forrester, 2010). Children who experience abuse and neglect are at risk for a variety of adverse outcomes as they mature and develop into adolescents and adults (Chalk, et al., May 2002). Yet little is known about the routine wellbeing of this population of children in Africa. Research on adverse experiences in childhood has been a substantially neglected area in Sub Saharan Africa including Nigeria. Yet the identification and assessment of the behavioural sequelae of ACEs is critical in developing responsive programs to help victims heal. This study therefore aims to determine the prevalence and interrelatedness of ACE and examine the association between ACE and sexual risk behaviours and sexual re-victimisation among young people. This would help develop a comprehensive approach for treatment programs for youths with ACEs within the context of the local culture in Nigeria. The global response to ACEs would also benefit from an insight into the parenting culture and information on the extent and consequences of ACEs in Nigeria.

Methodology*Study sample selection and data collection*

The study was conducted in Ibadan the capital of Oyo State, one of the 36 states of the Federal Republic of Nigeria. The study was a cross-sectional study with an exploratory component involving 347 in-school young people aged 10-24 years of both gender. Sample size was estimated with the WINPEPI software (Abrahamson,

2011), a minimum of 359 subjects were estimated using a prior estimate of the most prevalent ACE (physical abuse) which was 70% (Ige, Oguntayo, & Uchendu, 2009) at 95% confidence interval, 5% margin of error and a non response rate of 10%. Respondents were selected using a multistage random sampling from secondary schools located within Idikan, a low income urban community in Ibadan North West Local Government area of Ibadan. Validated anonymous self administered questionnaires adapted from the Adverse Childhood Experiences Questionnaires developed by the Centres for Disease Control and Prevention, USA (CDC, 2005) were used in data collection. Approval for the study was obtained from the University of Ibadan/University College Hospital Institutional review board. Permission was also obtained from parents and from the heads of the selected schools. Participation was voluntary and consent was obtained from participants after detailed information on the study had been given.

Measures

This study focussed on adverse childhood experiences that occurred within the context of the family before the respondent was 16 years old. Seven categories of stressful or traumatic childhood experiences were assessed: physical, emotional and sexual abuse; physical and emotional neglect; and household dysfunction.

ACEs

Neglect or abuse were rated on an ordinal scale ranging from never, rarely, sometimes to often, with the latter two responses classified as positive and scored 1, "never" and "rarely" were scored 0. Household dysfunction was ascertained with yes/no responses. The questions under each category of ACE were scored and scores of 1 or greater (i.e positive response to any of the questions in each category of ACE) was considered as exposure to that category of ACE. The questions used in assessing the ACEs are shown below

Psychological/Emotional

Did a parent or other adult in the household

- say hurtful things to you
- call you bad names

Physical

- punish you with a hard object
- beat you badly enough to be noticed
- hit you so hard you had to see a doctor.
- hit you so hard that you had marks or were injured?

Sexual

(Did an adult or person at least 5 years older ever . . .)

- Touch or fondle you in a sexual way?
- Have you touch their body in a sexual way?
- Attempt oral, anal, or vaginal intercourse with you?
- Actually have oral, anal, or vaginal intercourse with you?

Physical neglect

- Ever did not have enough to eat?
- Ever had to wear dirty clothes?
- Were not taken to the doctor when you needed it?

Emotional neglect

- Never felt loved
- Never made to feel important
- Ever felt that someone in your family hated you?
- Ever thought your parents wished you had never been born?

Household dysfunction

- Live with anyone who used street drugs?
- Live with anyone who was a problem drinker or alcoholic?

- Was a household member depressed or mentally ill?
- Did a household member attempt suicide?

Family connectedness

For assessing family connectedness participants were asked about how applicable to their lives each of following statements were

- feel close to family
- family a source of strength to you
- encouraged and supported by family

Sexual risk behaviour

The main outcome measure used in these analyses examined how many different types of risky behaviour the person reported practicing. A positive response to any of the following questions was classified as sexual risk behaviour

Age at first consensual intercourse less than 15 years

Multiple short-term sexual encounters;

Exchange of sex for money or gifts

Unprotected sexual intercourse

Unwanted pregnancy

Unsafe abortion

History of sexually transmitted infection

Analysis

Data was entered, cleaned and analyzed using Statistical Package for Social Sciences version 17 software. Frequencies and proportions were used to summarize variables of interest. Spearman's correlation coefficients were reported for correlation between ACE scores. Predictors of sexual risk behaviour and sexual re-victimization after the age of 16 years were determined with logistic regression analysis. Odds ratios (OR) and 95% confidence intervals (CI) are presented. The level of significance was set at 0.05, two-tailed.

Results

The response rate was 96.6%. The mean age of respondents was 15.9±3.9 years; more 267 (76.9%) of the respondents were female and a greater proportion 195(56.2) were in senior secondary school as shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Socio-demographic Characteristics

Socio-demographic Characteristics	N=347 (%)
Age groups	
10-14yrs	161 (46.4)
15-19yrs	132 (38.0)
20 and above	54 (15.6)
Gender	
Male	80 (23.1)
Female	267 (76.9)
Class	
Junior secondary classes 1-3	152(43.8)
Senior secondary classes 1-3	195(56.2)

Adverse Childhood Experiences

At least one form of adverse experience was reported by all respondents. The order of occurrence was: physical neglect (98%), emotional abuse (38.3%), physical abuse (35.7%) sexual abuse (29.1%) and emotional neglect (28.8%). Males and females did not significantly differ in each type of ACE except physical and sexual abuse in which higher proportions of males reported having been sexually abused in their childhood ($P < 0.05$). The median number of ACEs reported was 2 (range1-5). Females more often reported one ACE while males more often reported all five ACEs ($p < 0.05$). The only household dysfunction reported was problematic alcohol use. See Table 2

Table 2: Adverse Childhood Experiences

ACE	Total n (%)	Male n (%)	Female n (%)	p value
Physical neglect	340(98)	78(97.5)	262(98.1)	0.73
Emotional abuse	133(38.3)	35(43.8)	98(36.7)	0.26
Physical abuse	124(35.7)	44(55)	80(30)	<0.001
Sexual abuse	101(29.1)	33(41.3)	68(25.5)	0.01
Emotional neglect	100(28.8)	22(27.5)	78(29.2)	0.77
Number of abuses				
1	95(27.4)	13(16.3)	82(30.7)	0.01
2	115(33.1)	25(31.3)	90(33.7)	0.68
3	85(24.5)	24(30.0)	61(22.8)	0.19
4	85(24.5)	13(16.3)	29(10.9)	0.15
5	10(2.9)	5(6.3)	5(1.9)	0.04

Family connectedness

Most 277(79.8%) of the young people had a sense of family connectedness.

Interrelationships between categories of ACEs

Table 3 shows the interrelationships among categories of ACEs. More than half of the respondents who had experienced physical abuse also reported emotional and sexual abuse with significant correlation coefficients. Similarly, among those who had been emotionally abused 54.2% also reported being sexually abused. Although 95% of those who reported physical neglect also reported being emotionally neglected this was not significant ($p>0.05$).

Table 3: Relationship between forms of ACE

ACE	Emotional abuse R (%)	Sexual abuse R (%)	Physical neglect R (%)	Emotional neglect R (%)
Physical abuse	0.35* (53.4%)	0.24* (51.5%)	0.11 (35.6%)	0.02 (33.0%)
Emotional abuse		0.22* (54.5%)	-0.21* (37.9%)	-0.08 (42.0)
Sexual abuse			-0.24* (29.1%)	-0.05 (25%)
Physical neglect				0.17 (95%)

R= Correlation coefficient between ACE category subscale
% = percentage exposed to both categories

*= $p<0.001$

There was a significant association between sexual abuse and parental alcohol abuse ($p<0.05$) but not with other forms of ACEs. (See Table 4)

Table 4: Relationship between household dysfunction (problem drinking)

ACE	Problem drinking	No problem drinking	p value
Emotional neglect	8(8)	92(92)	0.333
No emotional neglect	13(5.3)	234(94.7)	
Physical neglect	21(6.2)	319(93.8)	Fishers 1.000
No physical neglect	0(0)	7(100)	
Sexual abuse	12(11.9)	89(88.1)	0.004
No sexual abuse	99(3.7)	237(96.3)	
Emotional abuse	10(7.5)	123(92.5)	0.366
No emotional abuse	11(5.1)	203(94.9)	
Physical abuse	8(6.5)	116(93.5)	0.816
No physical abuse	13(5.8)	210(94.2)	

Sexual Risk Behaviours

Current sexual activity was reported by 14.7% with the mean age at sexual debut being 16±3.9 years. In all, 15.0% reported at least one risky sexual behaviour; consisting of multiple sexual partners (6.6%), unprotected sexual intercourse (6.6%), history of sexually transmitted infection (5.5%), age at first sexual intercourse <15 years 5.5%, unsafe abortion (3.2%) and trading sex for money/gifts (2.6%). See Figure 1

Sexual re-victimization

After age 18, 32(9.2%) reported having been forced to have sexual intercourse

Associations between ACEs and Sexual Risk Behaviours

Table 5 shows the risk factors for sexual risk behaviours. Compared with 10-14 years, those aged 15-19 had about three times the risk while those aged 20 or older were about nine times more likely to exhibit sexual risk behaviour. Lack of family connectedness OR: 4.2 (1.5-11.6) and history of child sexual abuse OR: 6.9(3.5-14.1) were other risk factors. The odds of sexual risk behaviour increased by 2.3 (1.7-2.9) with each additional ACE reported. The only significant risk factor for sexual re-victimization was ACE of sexual abuse OR 12.062 (95% CI: 4.44- 32.74)

Table 5: ACEs and Sexual risk behaviour

Sexual risk behaviour	Odds Ratio (OR)	95% Confidence Interval	P value
Age 10-14	1.000		
Age 15-19	2.932	1.172-7.337	0.022
Age 20 and above	9.048	3.463- 23.639	<0.001
Parental connectedness	1.000		
No parental connectedness	4.246	1.507-11.964	0.006
Physical neglect	2.400	0.386-14.937	0.348
No physical neglect	1.000		
Emotional neglect	1.917	0.829-4.432	0.128
No emotional neglect	1.000		
Sexual abuse	6.586	3.163- 13.715	<0.001
No sexual abuse	1.000		
Emotional abuse	1.109	0.532-2.313	0.782
No emotional abuse	1.000		
Physical abuse	1.378	0.666-2.855	0.387
No physical abuse	1.000		
Household dysfunction (problem drinking)	1.321	0.352-4.950	0.401
No problem drinking	1.000		

Discussion

This survey of young people in a low income urban community in Nigeria has demonstrated the high prevalence of ACEs. All had experienced at least one ACE, most often physical neglect. This prevalence is higher than the two thirds who had experienced at least one ACE reported in some American studies (Dong, et al., 2004; Felitti, et al., 1998; Ramiro, Madrid, & Brown, 2010a) . It could be surmised that the high prevalence of physical neglect is an indicator of the poor child-rearing environment partly or mainly due to poverty and its social implications. There has been some speculation that the rates of adverse experiences and traumatic events could be higher in children from low- and middle-income countries (Connor & Butterfield, 2003). However more empirical data are needed to support this claim.

Consistent with other reports we found that ACEs tended to cluster with at least half reporting 2 or more ACEs (Felitti, et al., 1998). The interrelatedness was however moderate compared to the high probabilities of multiple ACEs exposures reported by Dong et al, (2004). Our findings are however similar to the estimates reported by another Nigerian study where the probability of being exposed to any additional category of ACE ranged from 43.5% to 63.2% (Oladeji, Makanjuola, & Gureje, 2010).

Other than physical neglect the prevalence of other forms of ACEs were similar to other studies (Felitti, et al., 1998) but lower than what has been reported by studies from developing countries (Jewkes, Dunkle, Mzikazi Nduna, Jamaa, & Purene, 2010; McCranna, Lator, & Katararo, 2006a; Ramiro, Madrid, & Brown, 2010b) The significantly higher prevalence of physical and sexual abuse among boys is an unusual finding. Although little attempt has been made to ascertain the prevalence of abuse of boys in Sub Saharan Africa, the few studies available have shown lower prevalence of sexual abuse in boys (Boden, Fergusson, & Horwood, 2009; McCranna, Lator, & Katararo, 2006b). This difference may be as a result of the different definitions of abuse employed.

The role of sexual abuse emerged in subsequent sexual risk behaviour has been previously documented (Boden, et al., 2009; Bornoalova, Gwadz, Kahler, Akin, & Lejuez, 2008; Fergusson, Horwood, & Lynskey, 1997). Survivors of severe sexual abuse have been shown to have the most abnormal profile of all victims of ACEs (Fitzpatrick, et al., 2009). This finding disagrees with those of (Jewkes, Dunkle, Nduna, Jamaa, & Purene, 2010; Kang, Deren, & Goldstein, 2002; Klein, Elifson, & Sterk, 2007; Medrano, Hatch, Zule, & Desmond, 2003) who concluded that physical and emotional abuse uniquely contribute to sexual risk behaviours. However the cumulative effect of ACEs on sexual behavioural problems is similar to other reports which have demonstrated dose-response relationship between the number of ACE exposures and health-risk behaviours (Dong, et al., 2004; S. Hillis & et al, 2001) . This further underscores the importance of simultaneously considering the role of multiple types of abuse in subsequent engagement in sexual risk behaviour. Childhood family connectedness was found to be protective against sexual risk behaviours as also found by S.D Hillis et al (2010) .

ACEs emerge as another unexplored part of children's lives in households that experience poverty. There is no doubt that children who experience a traumatic childhood are left with the scars that put them at elevated risk of other risk behaviours in adulthood. To ameliorate the impact of these ACEs we need to also pay attention to enhancing opportunities for positive family interactions as well as reducing exposure to abuse and neglect.

Limitations

There are certain limitations to be considered in this study. First, the sample included only young people in a low income urban community, a clearly vulnerable group for poor child rearing. It is uncertain how much the current study may be generalized considering that almost 70% of Nigerians live below the poverty line. The second limitation is the possibility of recall bias due to the unsubstantiated reports of ACEs based on self-reports only. However the common use of this methodology allows for a general assessment of the burden of ACEs. Lastly, although all participants came from a similar setting, the influence of other socio-demographic variables such as parental income and education were not explored.

References

- Abrahamson, J. H. (2011). WINPEPI updated: Computer program for epidemiologists, and their teaching potential. *Epidemiologic Perspectives & Innovations* 8(1).
- Anda, R., Felitti, V., Walker, J., Whitfield, C., Bremner, J., Perry, B., et al. (2006). The Enduring Effects of Abuse and Related Adverse Experiences in Childhood: A Convergence of Evidence from Neurobiology and Epidemiology. *European Archives of Psychiatry and Clinical Neuroscience*, 256(3), 174-186.
- Boden, J. M., Fergusson, D. M., & Horwood, L. J. (2009). Experience of sexual abuse in childhood and abortion in adolescence and early adulthood. *Child Abuse & Neglect*, 33, 870-876.
- Bornoalova, M. A., Gwadz, M. A., Kahler, C., Akin, W. M., & Lejuez, C. W. (2008). Sensation seeking and risk-taking propensity as mediators in the relationship between childhood abuse and HIV-related risk behavior. *Child Abuse & Neglect* 32, 99-109.
- CDC. (2005). Adverse childhood experiences study. Retrieved December 15, 2010, from <http://www.cdc.gov/nccdphp/ACE/questionnaires.htm>,
- Chalk, R., Gibbons, A., & Scarupa, H. J. (May 2002). The Multiple Dimensions of Child Abuse and Neglect: New Insights into an Old Problem. *Research Briefs* Retrieved January 20, 2011, from www.childtrends.org
- Connor, K., & Butterfield, M. (2003). Posttraumatic stress disorder. *Focus*, 1, 247 -262.

- Dong, M., Anda, R. F., Felitti, V. J., Dubea, S. R., Williamson, D. F., Thompson, T. J., et al. (2004). The interrelatedness of multiple forms of childhood abuse, neglect, and household dysfunction. *Child Abuse & Neglect* 28 771-784.
- Edwards, V., Anda, R., Dube, S., Dong, M., Chapman, D., & Felitti, V. (Eds.). (2005). *The wide-ranging health consequences of adverse childhood experiences*. Kingston: NJ:Civic Research Institute.
- Felitti, V. J., Anda, R. F., Nordenberg, D., Williamson, D. F., Spitz, A. M., Edwards, V., et al. (1998). Relationship of childhood abuse and household dysfunction to many of the leading causes of death in adults. The Adverse Childhood Experiences (ACE) Study. *American Journal of Preventive Medicine*, 14(4), 245-258.
- Fergusson, D. M., Horwood, L. J., & Lynskey, M. T. (1997). Childhood Sexual Abuse, Adolescent behaviors and Sexual Revictimization *Child Abuse & Neglect*, 21(8), 789-803.
- Fitzpatrick, M., Carr, A., Dooley, B., Flanagan-Howard, R., Flanagan, E., Tierney, K., et al. (2009). Profiles of adult survivors of severe sexual, physical and emotional institutional abuse in Ireland. *Child abuse review*.
- Forrester, A. (2010). *The Life Life-Time Health Effects of Adverse Childhood Experiences*. Connecticut: Clifford W. Beers Guidance Clinic.
- Hillis, S., & et al. (2001). Adverse childhood experiences and sexual risk behaviors in women: A retrospective cohort study. *Fam Plann Perspect*, 33, 206-211.
- Hillis, S. D., Anda, R. F., Dube, S. R., Felitti, V. J., Marchbanks, P. A., Macaluso, M., et al. (2010). The Protective Effect of Family Strengths in Childhood against Adolescent Pregnancy and Its Long-Term Psychosocial Consequences *The Permanente Journal*, 14(3).
- Ige, O. K., Oguntayo, M. A., & Uchendu, O. C. (2009). *Prevalence and Risk Factors of Child Abuse in Lagos State, Nigeria*. Paper presented at the International Conference on Urban Health Nairobi, Kenya
- Jewkes, R. K., Dunkle, K., Mzikazi Ndunad, J., Juma, P. N., & Purene, A. (2010). Associations between childhood adversity and depression, substance abuse and HIV and HSV2 incident infections in rural South African youth. *Child Abuse & Neglect*, 34, 833-841.
- Jewkes, R. K., Dunkle, K., Ndunad, M., Juma, N., & Purene, A. (2010). Associations between childhood adversity and depression, substance abuse and HIV and HSV2 incident infections in rural South African youth. *Child Abuse & Neglect* 34, 833-841.
- Kang, S.-Y., Deren, S., & Goldstein, M. F. (2002). Relationships between childhood abuse and neglect experience and HIV risk behaviors among methadone treatment drop-outs. *Child Abuse & Neglect* 26, 1275-1289.
- Klein, H., Elifson, K. W., & Sterk, C. E. (2007). Childhood neglect and adulthood involvement in HIV-related risk behaviors. *Child Abuse & Neglect* 31, 39-53.
- McCranna, D., Lalor, K., & Katabaro, J. K. (2006a). Childhood sexual abuse among university students in Tanzania *Child Abuse & Neglect*, 30, 1343-1351
- McCranna, D., Lalor, K., & Katabaro, J. K. (2006b). Childhood sexual abuse among university students in Tanzania *Child Abuse & Neglect* 30, 1343-1351
- Medrano, M. A., Hatch, J. P., Zule, W. A., & Desmond, D. P. (2003). Childhood trauma and adult prostitution behavior in a multiethnic heterosexual drug-using population. *American Journal of Drug and Alcohol Abuse*, 29, 463-486.
- Oladeji, B. D., Makanjuola, V. A., & Gureje, O. (2010). Family-related adverse childhood experiences as risk factors for psychiatric disorders in Nigeria. *The British Journal of Psychiatry*, 196, 186-191.
- Ramiro, L. S., Madrid, B. J., & Brown, D. W. (2010a). Adverse childhood experiences (ACE) and health-risk behaviors among adults in a developing country setting *Child Abuse & Neglect* 34, 842-855.
- Ramiro, L. S., Madrid, B. J., & Brown, D. W. (2010b). Adverse childhood experiences (ACE) and health-risk behaviors among adults in a developing country setting *Child Abuse & Neglect*, 34, 842-855.
- Sapp, M., & Vandeven, A. (2005). Update on childhood sexual abuse. *Curr Opin Pediatr* 17(2), 258-264.